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Improving multilabel text emotion detection with emotion interrelation anchors

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Title Page

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Improving Multilabel Text Emotion Detection with Emotion Interrelation Anchors

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Abstract

Emotion detection studies the problem of automatic identification of emotions expressed in text. Since multiple emotions may co-occur in a single text excerpt, state-of-the-art approaches often cast this multi-label classification task to multiple, independent binary classification tasks, each specialized for one emotion class. The main disadvantage of such approaches is that, by design, each binary classifier overlooks typical emotion interrelationships, such as co-occurrence (e.g., anger and fear) or mutual exclusiveness (e.g., sadness and joy). This paper proposes a simple and lightweight approach to re-introduce emotion interrelations into each binary classification task, where each binary classifier is able to understand the presence of other emotions, without directly inferring them. This is achieved by incorporating the proposed emotion anchors (i.e. features of representative emotional phrases) into the model of each binary classifier. More specifically, the model is trained to incorporate other emotions in its representation by learning the parameters of an attention mechanism. Based on experiments on multiple datasets, our approach improves emotion classification performance in both supervised and few-shot domain adaptation settings, outperforming standard binary models in terms of accuracy and macro averaged F1-scores. The approach is generic and can be applied to other interrelated multi-label binary classification tasks.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing, Emotion Detection, Multi-label Classification, Emotion Anchors

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1. Introduction

Understanding and accurately detecting emotions in various contexts, such as social media, customer feedback, and psychological research, has gained significant importance over the past few years. Although emotion detection has garnered attention from the scientific community, it remains a very challenging task, partly attributable to the absence of a singularly comprehensive delineation of human emotional states, as well as the subjective nature of the problem. Such challenges are even more pronounced in situations like natural disasters and global pandemics, as they necessitate rapid analyses which adds to the complexity of the problem (Blomeier et al., 2024). Moreover, annotating a dataset is a laborious process that consumes a substantial amount of time, which is not always feasible in short notice. Additionally, emotions are expressed in a multitude of ways during such disasters, often requiring implicit reasoning and event-specific information (Desai et al., 2020; Nagy and Stamberger, 2012).

Existing methodologies for tackling the emotion detection problem involve lexicon-based approaches, in which emotion keywords are assigned to a certain psychological state (Rabeya et al., 2017). The primary emotion of a sentence can then be determined by aggregating the emotions associated with each keyword, without requiring training data. Furthermore, machine learning approaches have been successfully employed, using feature vectors of emotion keywords, unigrams, emoticons, etc (Balabantaray et al., 2012; Roberts et al., 2012). The current state-of-the-art approaches use a BERT-based Transformer encoder (Devlin et al., 2018). BERT consists of multiple layers, each containing a multi-head self-attention mechanism followed by position-wise feedforward neural networks. The multi-head attention enables the model to focus on different parts of the sentence simultaneously, capturing various aspects of context. A sentence embedding can be extracted from the last layer. This embedding is typically used in a simple classifier, such as a one-layer neural network. The whole network is jointly fine-tuned for the downstream task.

In recent years, researchers are focused primarily on multi-label emotion classification (Alhuzali and Ananiadou, 2021; He and Xia, 2018). Perhaps the simplest approach to this end is by using a single multi-label classifier. This way emotion interrelations are easily introduced to the text representation as the feature space is the same for all emotions. Additional constraints can be incorporated through emotion model-related loss functions grounded in

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38 psychological theories of emotions (He and Xia, 2018; Deng and Ren, 2020).
39 However, machine learning models suffer greatly from the effects of class im-
40 balances (He and Garcia, 2009) that are prominent in expressed emotions
41 (Heiy and Cheavens, 2014; Zelenski and Larsen, 2000; Trampe et al., 2015)
42 calling for alternative methodologies. Another approach is to create separate
43 binary models for each emotion, where the text representation does not con-
44 sider intrinsic emotion interrelationships. An obvious limitation is increased
45 computational cost, since emotion detection requires the inference of multiple
46 models at the same time, only to infer a single text’s emotions. Nevertheless,
47 it has been shown that such approaches often lead to impressive performance
48 surpassing their multi-label equivalents (Desai et al., 2020). Similarly even
49 human annotators showcase a higher inter-annotator agreement when asked
50 to separately annotate each emotion (Sosea and Caragea, 2020). However,
51 the most important limitation though is that such approaches completely
52 disregard the complex interplay and dependencies that exist between emo-
53 tions, hindering our understanding of emotional states. In fact, psychology
54 studies (Plutchik, 1984; Cambria et al., 2012) have proposed that emotions
55 should not be expressed in isolation but rather in relation to one another,
56 drawing parallels between emotional states and a color wheel of continuous
57 values.

58 In this paper, we propose an approach to re-introduce emotion interrela-
59 tions while maintaining multiple independent binary classification problems,
60 by learning emotion representatives (we call them emotion anchors, here-
61 after). Emotion anchors of every class are defined in the feature space of
62 each and every binary classifier, thus the occurrence of each emotion can be
63 simply represented by its similarity with each emotion anchor. This way, we
64 combine the best of both worlds. Each binary classifier uses its own feature
65 space, thus it has good classification performance and does not suffer from
66 class imbalances. On the other hand, emotion interrelations are introduced
67 without needing the outputs of the other classifiers in the pack, since the an-
68 chors are already learned and stored in each independent emotion model. By
69 leveraging these emotion anchors, our approach improves the accuracy and
70 F1-score of multi-label emotion detection in multiple settings. Our method is
71 based on the smoothness assumption; examples that are close in the feature
72 space are more likely to belong to the same class. Thus, assuming that one
73 specific emotion is present in a text excerpt, we expect that the representa-
74 tion will have increased similarity with the corresponding emotion anchor.
75 Combining this assumption with the understanding that emotions often co-

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76 occur and influence one another, we claim that information can be extracted
77 by comparing the target text’s embedding with appropriate embeddings of
78 class representatives of other classes. To this end, an attention module is
79 used to learn, in a supervised manner, the expected similarity between dif-
80 ferent emotions within feature space. Furthermore, we show how this method
81 is also effective in few-shot domain adaptation settings. Overall, the main
82 contributions of our work are:

- 83 1. We propose AnchorBERT, a novel method for multi-label emotion de-
84 tection that reintroduces emotion interrelations into each binary clas-
85 sifier using emotion anchors.
- 86 2. We define and construct emotion anchors as representative sentence em-
87 beddings for each emotion class, enabling the modeling of co-occurrence
88 and exclusivity among emotions without requiring inter-class outputs.
- 89 3. We design an attention mechanism to incorporate anchor comparisons
90 into each classifier’s decision process, thus embedding emotion interre-
91 lations directly into the learned feature space.
- 92 4. We show that our method outperforms baseline and state-of-the-art
93 approaches across four diverse datasets, including in few-shot domain
94 adaptation settings.
- 95 5. We conduct extensive statistical significance and ablation studies, demon-
96 strating that our performance improvements are both significant and
97 interpretable.

98 In the subsequent sections of this paper, we will review the related work
99 and outline the architecture and design principles of our proposed method.
100 We will discuss the incorporation of emotion anchors in existing models and
101 their role in capturing emotion relationships. Moreover, we will present com-
102 prehensive experimental results and comparative analyses that demonstrate
103 the effectiveness of our approach over existing emotion classification tech-
104 niques.

105 **2. Related work**

106 *2.1. Deep Language Models*

107 Previous studies on emotion recognition leveraged hand-crafted lexicons,
108 such as WordNet-Affect (Strapparava et al., 2004) and EmoLex (Mohammad
109 and Turney, 2013), in order to identify emotion-indicative words and their

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110 respective labels. These word labels can be used, along with negation checks,
111 in order to determine the emotion label of each sentence (Wu et al., 2006).

112 More recently, emotion detection in text has been studied using machine
113 learning techniques. Supervised learning algorithms, such as Support Vec-
114 tor Machines (SVM) (Mygdalis et al., 2019), Naive Bayes, and Random
115 Forests, have been employed to classify text documents into emotion cat-
116 egories. These models utilize features like n-grams, part-of-speech tags, and
117 sentiment scores extracted from labeled datasets. Deep learning methods,
118 including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Net-
119 works (RNNs)(Majumder et al., 2019), have shown success in capturing se-
120 quential dependencies and contextual information, offering information-rich
121 embeddings.

122 However, thanks to recent advances in large pretrained language models,
123 most state-of-the-art approaches employ BERT-based methods (Ying et al.,
124 2019; Alhuzali and Ananiadou, 2021). BERT operates on the encoder of
125 the transformer architecture, which employs self-attention mechanisms to
126 capture contextual relationships between words in a sentence. Unlike tradi-
127 tional sequential models, BERT’s bidirectional nature allows it to consider
128 both preceding and succeeding words for each word in the input text. This
129 bidirectional context is captured through multihead self-attention layers that
130 weigh the importance of each word’s relationships with other words, enabling
131 BERT to generate contextually rich embeddings. BERT’s success hinges on
132 its pretraining strategy, where it learns to predict masked words in sentences,
133 leveraging surrounding context to develop deep contextual understanding and
134 capture intricate syntactic and semantic dependencies. This yields contextu-
135 alized embeddings for input tokens. Additionally, BERT’s versatility derives
136 from fine-tuning. Following pre-training on a large corpus, BERT is fine-
137 tuned on specific tasks using task-specific layers added atop the pre-trained
138 architecture.

139 Despite its efficacy, BERT tends to overlook the interdependencies among
140 masked positions due to the corruption of inputs with masks. In response to
141 this limitation, Yang et al. (2019) introduced XLNet, a novel approach that
142 involves maximizing the likelihood across various permutations of the factor-
143 ization order of conditional probabilities. This innovative technique enables
144 bidirectional context learning without the need for masking. Building on this
145 advancement, RoBERTa (Liu et al., 2019) emerged as a recent development,
146 matching the performance of the previous state-of-the-art language models.
147 This achievement was accomplished by training BERT on an even larger

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148 dataset and fine-tuning hyper-parameters to achieve optimal results. Addi-
149 tionally, RoBERTa introduced dynamic masking, where text is segmented
150 into chunks or spans, and within each span, some tokens are randomly se-
151 lected to be masked. Unlike BERT, which applies a fixed masking strategy
152 during pretraining, RoBERTa employs a more varied and adaptable masking
153 technique. This dynamic masking approach helps prevent the model from
154 overly relying on the specific position of masked tokens and encourages it to
155 learn more robust features.

156 Although fine-tuning BERT followed by a simple one-layer neural network
157 yields impressive results, recent research has focused on further customizing
158 BERT for the emotion detection task. In Alhuzali and Ananiadou (2021)
159 instead of using the whole input text’s representation, authors cast multi-
160 label emotion classification as a span-prediction problem. This means the
161 encoder was presented with two segments, the first being the label names (e.g.
162 “anger anticipation disgust”) and the second being the text to be evaluated.
163 Let $\{\mathcal{S}_i, \mathbf{y}_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a dataset of N sentence samples \mathcal{S}_i , with a corresponding
164 label vector $\mathbf{y}_i \in \{0, 1\}^C$, where $\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_C\}$ is the emotion set and
165 $|\mathcal{C}| = C$ the cardinality of the emotion set. We denote $|\mathcal{S}_i|$ the length of the
166 i -th input text. We also define special tokens $[CLS]$ and $[SEP]$ as a token
167 used for obtaining the whole input’s representation and a sentence separator
168 token respectively. Using this notation, the encoder’s output $\mathbf{E}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{l \times d}$ is:

$$\mathbf{E}_i = BERT([CLS] + \mathcal{C} + [SEP] + \mathcal{S}_i), \quad (1)$$

169 where $l = 2 + C + |\mathcal{S}_i|$ and d the length of the input and the dimensional size
170 of the model, respectively.

171 Following the encoder, a one-layer neural network, consisting of a tanh
172 activation function was used to map the encoding only using the label seg-
173 ment, i.e., $L_1(\cdot) : \mathbf{E} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{C \times d}$. A second layer i.e., $L_2(\cdot) : \mathbf{E} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^C$ followed
174 by a sigmoid activation function $\sigma(\cdot)$ was used to obtain the final prediction
175 $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \in \{0, 1\}^C$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = (\sigma \circ L_2 \circ L_1)(\mathbf{E}) \quad (2)$$

176 This method achieved state of the art results in English, Arabic and Spanish
177 emotion classification sets (Mohammad et al., 2018).

178 At NLPCC 2018 (Wang et al., 2018), numerous contributions were made
179 in the field of multi-label emotion detection in code-switching text. Among
180 these, Zhang et al. (2018) stood out as it achieved the highest performance

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181 by employing ensemble learning alongside random undersampling. Subse-
182 quently, Deng and Ren (2020) introduced MEDA, a hierarchical approach
183 that combines a BERT encoder, an emotion lexicon, and a bidirectional
184 GRU network to enhance emotion correlation learning. The evaluation on
185 NLPCC 2018 demonstrated a substantial improvement over binary relevance,
186 classifier chains and other baseline approaches.

187 Recent work has continued to advance multi-label emotion detection by
188 exploring more adaptive architectures and real-world challenges. Fu et al.
189 (2024) propose a multi-label class incremental learning framework for emo-
190 tion decoding by introducing augmented emotional semantics through an
191 emotional relation graph and knowledge distillation techniques. Their ap-
192 proach addresses the challenge of catastrophic forgetting and showcases ro-
193 bust performance in scenarios with evolving emotion classes and label spar-
194 sity.

195 Belay et al. (2024) conducted a comprehensive evaluation of large lan-
196 guage models on Ethiopian and English multilabel emotion detection. Their
197 findings reveal that even advanced LLMs struggle with fine-grained multi-
198 label emotion understanding in both low and high-resource languages, high-
199 lighting the importance of task-specific methodologies.

200 *2.2. Multi-label classification*

201 Upon extracting the pertinent features from the target text, three primary
202 paradigms surface for classifying the text within the chosen emotion classes
203 (He and Xia, 2018; Tsoumakas and Katakis, 2007):

204 **Threshold Dependent Neural Networks (TDNN)** typically involves
205 constructing a single neural network to generate probabilities for all labels.
206 Subsequently, a threshold mechanism is employed to convert the multi-class
207 probabilities into multi-label outputs. This way, the feature space is the
208 same for all emotions, and the introduction of class inter-relations is trivial.
209 However, the selection of the threshold function poses several challenges and
210 is a subject of significant research in the field (Zhang and Zhou, 2006; Read
211 and Perez-Cruz, 2014; Nam et al., 2014).

212 **Binary Relevance Neural Networks (BRNN)** construct an inde-
213 pendent binary neural network for each label, considering multi-label clas-
214 sification as a set of isolate binary classification tasks. Predictions can sub-
215 sequently be determined by obtaining the class specific outputs. Although
216 this method ignores class dependencies and consumes more resources due to
217 the need of training as many classifiers as there are classes, each model is

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218 tasked with solving a more specific problem. Additionally labels can be bal-
219 anced leading to better performance especially when faced with large label
220 imbalances. For these reasons, this is the approach followed in this paper.

221 **Joint Binary Neural Network (JBNN)** He and Xia (2018) proposed
222 that the representation of the text be fed to a set of logistic functions instead
223 of a softmax function, leading to a binary decision without a need for selecting
224 a threshold value. This enables the multiple binary classifications to be
225 carried out synchronously in one neural network framework.

226 Specifically for binary classifiers, various methods have tried to incorpo-
227 rate emotion interrelations. One widely used technique involves defining an
228 ordered classifier chain (Read et al., 2009). In this approach, each model
229 takes into account the predictions of its predecessors as additional features.
230 However, this method has the drawback of propagating errors from earlier
231 predictions and necessitates serial inference, resulting in increased compu-
232 tational complexity compared to our proposed approach. Furthermore, em-
233 ploying this method for emotion detection assumes a predefined correlation
234 order for emotions, an assumption that may not hold. Another strategy
235 involves ensemble learning with random chain orders (Li and Zhou, 2013).
236 While this approach can mitigate the correlation order issue to some extent,
237 it significantly increases computational complexity. In contrast, the stacking
238 approach (Godbole and Sarawagi, 2004) utilizes two sets of binary classifiers,
239 with the second set considering the predictions of the first set before making
240 the final prediction. While this method encompasses all potential label cor-
241 relations, it introduces considerably higher computational complexity due to
242 the use of twice as many classifiers. In contrast, our approach keeps the bi-
243 nary models separated and introduces correlation through pre-calculated em-
244 beddings, making no assumptions about a specific emotion order and adding
245 no extra computational complexity.

246 *2.3. Emotion detection in Disaster Management scenarios*

247 Beyond the related work in emotion detection, disaster management sce-
248 narios impose additional constraints to the problem. Desai et al. (2020) in-
249 troduced an emotion dataset spanning three hurricanes to acilitate research
250 in disaster-centric domains. Their analysis reveled that BERT outperformed
251 newer models. However, models trained on a general domain performed
252 poorly on the disaster data, partially due to intricacies of the dataset, such
253 emotions being implicitly expressed.

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254 Additionally, when analyzing tweets from the COVID-19 pandemic, Sosea
255 et al. (2021) focused on the time-criticality of such events by adapting the
256 idea of noisy student training (Ying et al., 2019) to natural language in order
257 to reduce the need for labeled data.

258 By introducing a noising function in the student’s input, Noisy Student
259 exposes the student to more difficult learning environments, usually leading
260 to better performance compared to the teacher. In the context of Natural
261 Language two noising functions were used: 1) Synonym replacement: Where
262 between one and three words in each input were replaced with a synonym;
263 2) Back-translation: Where the input text is subject to a chain of transla-
264 tion before it is converted back to English (e.g. English-French-...-English).
265 Larger chains typically lead to more noise.

266 To address the problems identified in Sosea et al. (2021), we propose an
267 alternative method for domain adaptation requiring no additional unlabeled
268 data from the target domain. Finally, regarding Desai et al. (2020) we pose
269 that implicit emotions can be better identified by reintroducing emotion in-
270 terrelationships that are ignored in their analysis.

271 3. Proposed Method

272 3.1. AnchorBERT Framework

273 The proposed framework, AnchorBERT, aims to re-introduce label in-
274 terrelations into each binary emotion classification task, without directly
275 inferring each emotion. This is achieved through an attention mechanism,
276 that compares the text’s representation with a set of predetermined anchors.
277 These comparisons result in an enriched embedding, encoding both a repre-
278 sentation of the text, as well as a representation of the text’s similarity to
279 each emotion. Figure 3.1 presents this framework, AnchorBERT.

280 3.2. Formal description

281 Let $\{\mathcal{S}_i, \mathbf{y}_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a dataset of N sentence samples \mathcal{S}_i with a corresponding
282 label vector $\mathbf{y}_i \in \{0, 1\}^C$, where $y_i^{(j)}$ is an index that indicates the presence of
283 an emotion j . BERT is used as an encoder function that takes sentences as
284 input and converts them to column vectors, i.e., $BERT(\cdot) : \mathcal{S} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{d \times (|\mathcal{S}_i| + t)}$,
285 where d is the dimensionality of the feature vector, $|\mathcal{S}_i|$ is the length of
286 sentence i after tokenization, and t is the number of special tokens added.
287 For the purpose of text classification we only utilize the $[CLS]$ token, that
288 is added at the start of the input text in order to obtain a representation of

Figure 1: Illustration of the proposed method, AnchorBERT. Given an input sentence, a base encoder is leveraged to extract the contextualized word representation. Next, a class anchor is used for each emotion in order to enrich the text’s representation. To this end a multi-headed attention module is employed. Finally a feed forward neural network projects the enriched representation into the binary task at hand. During training, anchors are sampled randomly, while during inference, the mean representation of each anchor is used. We illustrate our model both during training (left) and inference (right).

the entire sentence. Without this special token BERT would only produce a representation for each word separately. Therefore for each sentence \mathcal{S}_i the corresponding feature representation is $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

The anchor vectors \mathbf{a}_i are defined for the cases where a sample (\mathcal{S}_i, y_i) contains only one emotion, i.e., $\sum_{j=1}^C y_i^{(j)} = 1$. We argue that these examples best implicitly describe their respective class, without dependencies on any other classes. Therefore anchors can be used as a source of indirect information on their corresponding emotion. Additionally, based on the smoothness assumption, we posit that like most real-world scenarios, emotions tends to exhibit a certain degree of continuity and gradual change. This assumption is consistent with many psychological theories on human emotions existing in a spectrum (Plutchik, 1984; Russell, 1980; Mehrabian, 1980).

In order to extract this information we train C binary BERT models θ_i using the baseline method, one for each emotion class. Each model is tasked with predicting the existence of a single emotion, therefore it is trained on a subset of the available data $\{\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_i, \tilde{y}_i\}_{i=1}^{N'} \subseteq \{\mathcal{S}_i, \mathbf{y}_i\}_{i=1}^N$, where $\tilde{y}_i \in \{0, 1\}$ denotes the presence of the respective emotion in the sentence. All models

are trained to minimize the binary cross-entropy loss on their subset of data:

$$\frac{1}{N'} \sum_{i=1}^{N'} \mathcal{L}(\tilde{y}_i, f(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_i, \theta^t)). \quad (3)$$

Since the $[CLS]$ token is meant to encode sentence-level features, the $[CLS]$ output of the trained binary model is considered as an accurate representation of the input text with regard to its emotions after fine-tuning. For this reason we extract every anchor representation with the respective emotion’s model. The anchor vectors for class c are defined for the anchors i , where $y_i^{(c)} = 1$. We denote the anchor representations for each class c as \mathcal{A}_c .

We argue that evaluating a new sentence with a binary model specifically trained on class c completely disregards its inter-dependency with other classes. At the same time, using a single multi-label model, despite capturing class interactions, has been shown to perform worse in several emotion detection settings (Desai et al., 2020; Sosea et al., 2021). Therefore we aim to compare each input sentence with anchors of every emotion as a means of reintroducing emotion relations. When training our binary model, we select one anchor randomly from the pool of available anchors for each emotion. Then, a single multi-headed attention module is used c times, once for each emotion, with the sentence $[CLS]$ token as the query vector and each selected anchor’s representation \mathbf{a}_c^* as the key and value. We use the multi-headed attention definition from Vaswani et al. (2017) as follows:

$$MultiHead(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = Concat(\mathbf{head}_1, \dots, \mathbf{head}_h) \mathbf{W}^0, \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{head}_i = Attention(\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{W}_i^Q, \mathbf{K} \mathbf{W}_i^K, \mathbf{V} \mathbf{W}_i^V)$$

is an attention head attending to a subspace of the initial representations, \mathbf{Q} is the query, \mathbf{K} is the key, \mathbf{V} is the value and \mathbf{W} are the learnable weights.

Since the same multi-headed attention mechanism is utilized between every set of sentence feature vectors and selected anchors, the text’s similarity with an anchor of class c is defined as:

$$\mathbf{s}_c = MultiHead(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{a}_c^*, \mathbf{a}_c^*), \quad (5)$$

where:

$$c \in [1, \mathcal{C}]$$

331 The final representation $\mathbf{h} \in \mathcal{R}^{c \times d}$ is derived from concatenating the
 332 outputs of each attention comparison and the original feature vector:

$$\mathbf{h} = \text{Concat}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_n). \quad (6)$$

333 During inference, we aim to eliminate the instability introduced by randomly
 334 picking anchors. In order to achieve this, the mean representation of each
 335 emotion anchor set is used, i.e.:

$$\bar{\mathbf{a}}_c = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \mathcal{A}_c^{(n)}. \quad (7)$$

Table 1: Positive emotion occurrences in CovidEMO, HurricaneEMO and CancerEMO.

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Set</i>	<i>ANG</i>	<i>ANT</i>	<i>DIS</i>	<i>FEA</i>	<i>JOY</i>	<i>SAD</i>	<i>SUR</i>	<i>TRU</i>
	<i>Train</i> (#)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CovidEMO	<i>Validation</i> (#)	327	296	163	179	186	388	86	89
	<i>Test</i> (#)	374	296	214	149	170	403	83	78
	<i>Train</i>	8779	1278	2108	3680	1906	2973	3860	3046
HurricaneEMO	<i>Validation</i>	1113	148	267	447	237	364	467	374
	<i>Test</i>	1108	180	256	451	209	370	506	388
	<i>Train</i> (#)	344	180	369	2148	2410	1427	307	756
CancerEMO	<i>Validation</i> (#)	41	17	45	260	311	196	51	95
	<i>Test</i> (#)	34	21	33	286	301	180	55	93

Table 2: Positive emotion occurrences in NLPCC 2018.

<i>Dataset</i>	<i>Set</i>	<i>Anger</i>	<i>Fear</i>	<i>Happiness</i>	<i>Sadness</i>	<i>Surprise</i>
	<i>Train</i>	462	520	1444	878	878
NLPCC 2018	<i>Validation</i>	108	128	380	208	117
	<i>Test</i>	120	85	220	120	92

336 In the case of few-shot domain adaptation, the model is fine-tuned on a
 337 source/general domain (i.e. GoEmotions (Demszky et al., 2020)) and given
 338 few relevant samples, while it is evaluated on the target domain. Anchors
 339 can either be chosen from the target or the source domain. We find that
 340 aligning the anchors with the respective input domain works best as a means
 341 of capturing inter-domain similarities. Therefore, anchors are picked from the
 342 source domain during training, and from the target domain during inference.

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343 Finally a feed-forward network, consisting of one layer followed by a *ReLU*
344 activation function is used to combine the text’s *[CLS]* representation with
345 the anchor comparisons, while a second layer reduces the dimension to 2 in
346 order to classify the existence of the particular emotion i.e., $FFN(\cdot) : \mathbf{h} \mapsto$
347 \mathbb{R}^2 . The final prediction is made according to the equation:

$$\hat{y} = \operatorname{argmax}(FFN(\mathbf{h})). \quad (8)$$

348 Our proposed model θ^p is trained to minimize the cross-entropy loss using
349 back-propagation, much like the baseline models, given the extra information
350 of anchor representations:

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^{N'} \mathcal{L}(\tilde{y}_i, f(\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_i, \mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2, \dots, \mathcal{A}_C, \theta^p)). \quad (9)$$

351 4. Experiments

352 The proposed network architecture was evaluated both for supervised
353 emotion detection and for few-shot domain adaptation, on four datasets, i.e.
354 CovidEMO, HurricaneEMO, CancerEMO and NLPCC 2018, where authors
355 find the best approach to be constructing binary relevance neural networks.
356 For comparison purposes, we employed the proposed architecture based on
357 the BERT model, which authors found to perform best on each dataset.
358 Wherever publicly available, we have adapted our method to the source code
359 from the paper authors. In the following subsections, we will present im-
360 plementation details, datasets, and task settings for each one. Next, we
361 will present the results of our method compared to baselines and compet-
362 ing methods. Finally, we will provide an analysis of the results, discuss the
363 limitations, and perform a significance analysis of the improved performance.

364 4.1. Implementation Details

365 We implement all models in Pytorch (Paszke et al., 2017) and ran all ex-
366 periments on an Nvidia GeForce GTX 1080 with 8 GB of memory. We also
367 train all BERT models utilizing the open-source Hugging-Face implemen-
368 tation (Wolf et al., 2019). For experiment on HurricaneEMO and Cancer-
369 EMO, we choose "bert-base-uncased", for experiments on CovidEMO "Covid-
370 twitter-bert" developed by Müller et al. (2023) and for NLPCC 2018 "bert-
371 base-chinese". For optimization Adam was used (Kingma and Ba, 2014).
372 Finally all models are trained for a maximum of 5 epochs with early stopp-
373 ing.

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374 4.2. Datasets and task settings

375 We use the following four datasets to evaluate the proposed models:

- 376 • **CovidEMO** (Sosea et al., 2021) is a dataset of $\sim 3\text{K}$ tweets in English annotated with Plutchik-8 emotions (Plutchik, 1984), distributed across 18 months of the COVID-19 pandemic.
- 379 • **HurricaneEMO** (Desai et al., 2020) is a dataset of $\sim 18\text{K}$ tweets in English, spanning hurricanes Harvey, Irma and Maria, annotated with Plutchik-8 emotions.
- 382 • **CancerEMO** (Sosea and Caragea, 2020) is a dataset of $\sim 8.5\text{K}$ tweets in English, sampled from an online cancer survivors network, annotated with Plutchik-8 emotions.
- 385 • **NLPCC 2018** is a Chinese code-switching twitter dataset, annotated with 5 emotion (i.e. anger, fear, happiness, sadness, surprise)

387 Tables 1 and 2 summarizes these datasets, including the number of emotion instances in the train, validation and test sets for each emotion. We draw attention to the large imbalances between different emotions.

390 CovidEMO’s 3 thousand tweets force us to implement anchors with the goal of domain adaptation. Following the original paper, we fine-tune CT-BERT on GoEmotions (Demszky et al., 2020) with early stopping on the in-domain validation set. After identifying the anchors from both the validation and the train set, we extract the corresponding $[CLS]$ tokens using the trained models. As discussed in Section 3, we find that it is important for the anchors and the input sentence to be from the same domain, i.e. we use GoEmotion’s anchors during training and CovidEMO’s mean anchors during validation and testing.

399 On the contrary HurricaneEMO, CancerEMO and NLPCC 2018 are large enough to implement supervised learning techniques. Binary models are trained on the provided splits, and corresponding anchors are identified by reconstructing the dataset as multi-label, before training AnchorBERT.

403 4.3. Results

404 Following the respective dataset authors, we report the average performance of 5 different runs for CovidEMO, CancerEMO and NLPCC 2018 and 10 runs for HurricaneEMO. Since the former’s test set is imbalanced, while the latter’s not, we present the Macro-F-1 scores and accuracy respectively.

Subsequently, we show the results of our model in Table 3. We observe that *AnchorBERT* improves upon vanilla BERT by around 0.9% in terms of F1-score on CancerEMO. Furthermore it surpasses previous state of the art models by more than 2%, according to their reported performances.

Table 3: Macro F-1 scores of current state of baseline $BERT_{base}$, state-of-the-art $eMLM$ (Sosea and Caragea, 2021) and our proposed model on CancerEMO.

<i>Model</i>	<i>ANG</i>	<i>ANT</i>	<i>DIS</i>	<i>FEA</i>	<i>JOY</i>	<i>SAD</i>	<i>SUR</i>	<i>TRU</i>	<i>AVG</i>
$BERT_{base}^*$ (Sosea and Caragea, 2020)	0.68	0.70	0.59	0.77	0.81	0.71	0.68	0.67	0.701
$eMLM$ (Sosea and Caragea, 2021)	0.69	0.78	0.58	0.77	0.85	0.73	0.68	0.67	0.718
<i>AnchorBERT</i>	0.691	0.845	0.729	0.715	0.831	0.719	0.735	0.652	0.74

Table 4 presents the performance of our proposed approach (*AnchorBERT*) on CovidEMO.

Table 4: F1-scores using Covid Tweeter BERT (CT-BERT), the SSL techniques proposed by the dataset authors (SSL), and our proposed model (*AnchorBERT*).

<i>Model</i>	<i>ANG</i>	<i>ANT</i>	<i>DIS</i>	<i>FEA</i>	<i>JOY</i>	<i>SAD</i>	<i>SUR</i>	<i>TRU</i>	<i>AVG</i>
CT-BERT	0.735	0.577	0.629	0.644	0.725	0.717	0.617	0.520	0.644
Noisy-SSL (Sosea et al., 2021)	0.741	0.554	0.657	0.651	0.741	0.726	0.632	0.532	0.654
<i>AnchorBERT</i>	0.759	0.584	0.652	0.660	0.747	0.735	0.637	0.553	0.666

When it comes to CovidEMO, our method outperforms baseline models on all emotions, with an average improvement of 2.2%. Compared to the reported performance of Noisy-Self Supervised Learning (Sosea et al., 2021), our model showcases higher F1-scores on all but one emotions. It should be noted that the SSL technique utilizes knowledge distillation and self-training to iteratively train two models in a teacher-student framework, meaning several training iterations are needed, along with a large set of unlabeled data. In contrast our approach requires no additional data and only 2 training iterations per emotion, one for the anchor representation encoder and one for *AnchorBERT*.

Table 5: Accuracy scores using BERT base and our proposed model (*AnchorBERT*) on the HurricaneEMO dataset.

<i>Model</i>	<i>ANG</i>	<i>ANT</i>	<i>DIS</i>	<i>FEA</i>	<i>JOY</i>	<i>SAD</i>	<i>SUR</i>	<i>TRU</i>	<i>AVG</i>
$BERT_{base}$	0.676	0.750	0.668	0.683	0.540	0.585	0.557	0.674	0.641
<i>AnchorBERT</i>	0.714	0.749	0.670	0.679	0.557	0.615	0.564	0.691	0.655

Similarly, our model outperformed the base model in 6 out of 8 emotions on HurricaneEMO. As shown in Table 5 AnchorBERT achieves an average improvement of 1.4%.

Finally, we present our model’s performance on NLPCC 2018 in Table 6. We compare our method to baseline BERT and DeepIntell (Zhang et al., 2018), the top submission at the NLPCC 2018 shared task using the task’s official evaluation metric (macro f1). We find that binary relevance BERT models already outperform DeepIntell by nearly 3%. The incorporation of our method yields an additional 3% improvement over the baseline, while consistently achieving superior scores across all emotions.

Table 6: F-1 scores of *DeepIntell*, baseline *BERT* and *AnchorBERT* on NLPCC 2018 per emotion and overall Macro F-1 score.

<i>Model</i>	<i>ANG</i>	<i>FEA</i>	<i>HAP</i>	<i>SAD</i>	<i>SUR</i>	<i>F1</i>
<i>DeepIntell</i>	0.543	0.264	0.734	0.616	0.418	0.515
<i>BERT_{base}</i>	0.613	0.395	0.753	0.531	0.418	0.542
<i>AnchorBERT</i>	0.629	0.415	0.777	0.578	0.468	0.573

5. Analysis

Overall, the proposed AnchorBERT approach outperforms baseline BERT methods in all four datasets. The results show that AnchorBERT can successfully re-introduce interrelations between classes for the emotion detection task, based on representative “anchors”. Our method is tested on a variety of domains, ranging from natural disasters to health related texts, indicating that it is suitable for generic emotion detection. Although AnchorBERT was only tested for emotion detection, the underlying principle can be extended to a wide range of multi-label tasks to leverage interrelationships between classes.

The premise of our method also sets a number of limitations. One key consideration is the degree of interdependence among emotion classes. AnchorBERT derives its effectiveness from the presence of co-occurring emotions and their interdependencies. In cases where classes are weakly dependent or exhibit a high degree of mutual exclusiveness, the relative increase in performance may be less pronounced. It is essential to recognize that the method’s

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450 performance is contingent on the data’s inherent relationships between emo-
451 tions. In scenarios where certain emotions have a strict mutual exclusiveness,
452 our attention mechanism may not automatically disregard unrelated anchors
453 unless an adequate number of training examples are provided. Addressing
454 these issues and optimizing our method for specific datasets with unique
455 characteristics remains a potential area for future research.

456 Furthermore, while AnchorBERT improves multi-label emotion detection,
457 it is important to consider the computational cost associated with fine-tuning
458 separate binary BERT models for each emotion class. Future work could ex-
459 plore strategies to reduce computational overhead while maintaining or even
460 enhancing performance. Additionally, the choice of anchors and the impact
461 of anchor selection on model performance warrant further investigation. De-
462 veloping a systematic approach to anchor selection and evaluating its impact
463 on different tasks and datasets could provide valuable insights.

464 5.1. Ablation Study

465 To further validate the efficacy of our proposed method, we present an
466 analysis of the impact of the percentage of anchors used on the model’s
467 performance. This analysis was conducted on the validation set of the Can-
468 cerEMO dataset. The lower bound (i.e., 0%) corresponds to the baseline
469 BERT model, while the upper bound (i.e., 100%) indicates that all anchors
470 in the dataset were utilized.

471 The resulting performance curve (Figure 2) exhibits an initial phase of
472 small increases in the F1-score, followed by a phase of more rapid increases,
473 and finally, a return to smaller increases as the percentage of anchors ap-
474 proaches 100%. This S-shaped curve indicates that while adding more an-
475 chors consistently improves performance, the rate of improvement varies,
476 with the most significant gains occurring in the middle range of anchor per-
477 centages. We pose that the reason for this S-curve is because using few an-
478 chors offers little to no contextual information, while as we approach 100%,
479 adding more anchors “diminishes” the additional information gained. Based
480 on these findings, we opted to use all available anchors for all experiments
481 reported in this paper.

482 5.2. Significance Analysis

483 After obtaining the performance of the competing methods in all ex-
484 periments, we determined whether the observed differences of the proposed
485 method with the competition are statistically significant, or not, by using the

Figure 2: Model performance vs. percentage of anchors used

486 implementation from Ulaş et al. (2012); Mygdalis and Pitas (2022); Mygdalis
 487 et al. (2019). To this end, we have tested the null hypotheses that all classi-
 488 fiers perform the same, using the Friedman’s test. The mean ranks for each
 489 algorithm according to their performance in all classification problems are
 490 shown in Table 7. By employing 4 datasets, three of which comprise of 8
 491 binary tasks and one of 5 and using 2 classifiers, the degrees of freedom are
 492 equal to 28. The Friedman statistic was equal to $\chi^2_{\mathcal{F}} = 12.45$, and the criti-
 493 cal value was 3.84. Therefore, the null hypotheses that all classifiers perform
 494 the same, was rejected. After employing the Nemenyi post-hoc procedure for
 495 pairwise comparison, using a significance level of 95%, i.e., $\alpha = 0.05$, the Criti-
 496 cal Distance (CD) was found at 0.36, which means that the proposed method
 497 performed significantly better than the baseline BERT method. Moreover,
 498 we have also used the Bergman-Hommel’s posthoc procedure, which ampli-
 499 fies the test power by using an exhaustive sets of hypothesis, i.e hypothesis
 500 that can be true at the same time. The critical distance was calculated at
 501 0.31. Therefore, the proposed method performs significantly better than the
 502 base models.

503 To evaluate the significance of our model’s performance against other
 504 domain adaptation methods, we conduct the Friedman’s test between Noisy-
 505 SSL, AnchorBERT, and the common baseline approach. The Friedman

Table 7: Statistical test details

<i>Model</i>	<i>BERT_{base}</i>	<i>Proposed</i>
<i>Mean ranks</i>	1.83	1.17
<i>Posthoc Procedure</i>	<i>Nemenyi</i>	<i>Bergman-Hommel's</i>
a	0.05	0.05
CD	0.36	0.31

506 statistic was equal to $\chi^2_{\mathcal{F}} = 12.3$, and the critical value was 6, indicating
 507 our method performs significantly better at the 95% significance level.

508 5.3. Computational Complexity Analysis

509 In the context of our research, it is crucial to assess the computational
 510 complexity of our proposed method. We have observed that our approach
 511 demonstrates a computational complexity profile closely resembling that of
 512 BERT. However, it is worth noting that our method introduces an negligible
 513 delay attributable to the inclusion of a single additional attention layer. This
 514 added layer contributes minimally to the overall computational load, ensuring
 515 that the overall complexity of our method remains largely comparable to that
 516 of the backbone selected. Timing our approach reveals that the attention
 517 operation accounts for less than 1% of the overall inference time.

518 Furthermore, as each class's model operates independently of the others,
 519 in time-sensitive applications, parallel inference can be executed. Considering
 520 additional delays, such as data loading, we determined that for an 8-class
 521 classification task, the overall delay in comparison to a single model is under
 522 2%. This implies that a fully parallelized implementation is 7.92 times faster
 523 than utilizing a single GPU.

524 An additional factor that adds to the computational cost is the extraction
 525 of anchor representations from the baseline models. While the resulting
 526 delay is not insignificant, we propose that this process can be seamlessly
 527 incorporated into the hyper-parameter grid search process, by storing the
 528 anchor embeddings during inference. This approach effectively reduces both
 529 the environmental and time-related overheads. Additionally, since baseline
 530 experiments are conducted for all new systems, the training of the anchor
 531 extraction model can also be integrated into this process, further diminishing
 532 the computational expenses.

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533 6. Conclusion

534 This work introduced a novel approach to multi-label emotion detection
535 called AnchorBERT, which leverages the concept of “emotion anchors” to
536 enhance the understanding and detection of emotions in textual data. Our
537 method was extensively evaluated on four diverse datasets, spanning vari-
538 ous domains from the COVID-19 pandemic to natural disasters and health-
539 related texts, for both supervised learning and few-shot domain adaptation.
540 The results clearly demonstrated the effectiveness of AnchorBERT, as it con-
541 sistently outperformed baseline BERT methods in terms of emotion detection
542 accuracy and F1-score across all datasets.

543 One of the key strengths of AnchorBERT is its ability to re-establish the
544 intricate interrelations between emotion classes, providing a more compre-
545 hensive and nuanced understanding of emotional states within text. This
546 approach not only enhances performance in scenarios where emotions co-
547 occur but also shows promise in capturing the subtleties of emotion inter-
548 dependencies. Moreover, AnchorBERT’s versatility was showcased as it ex-
549 celled in multiple domains, indicating its suitability for generic emotion de-
550 tection tasks. However, it is essential to acknowledge certain limitations of
551 our approach, particularly in cases where emotion classes exhibit weak inter-
552 dependence or mutual exclusiveness. While AnchorBERT offers substantial
553 improvements in multi-label emotion detection, the degree of label inter-
554 dependency remains a crucial factor in its performance. Furthermore, the
555 computational cost associated with training separate binary BERT models
556 for each emotion class should be considered.

557 Looking ahead, the principles underlying AnchorBERT hold promise for
558 extending its application beyond emotion detection to a wide range of multi-
559 label classification tasks, spanning various domains and modalities (e.g. vi-
560 sion, audio etc). Next since anchors contain a single emotion, their represen-
561 tation could be extracted by a single multi-class model, in order to reduce
562 the computational complexity. Finally, emotion anchors can be utilized as a
563 complimentary input to other tasks (e.g. sentiment analysis, urgency detec-
564 tion), or inversely, emotion detection can utilize representations obtained by
565 different tasks’ classes.

566 7. Ethics Statement

567 This work explores the task of emotion detection in text, which has impli-
568 cations for mental health research, user behavior analysis, and social media

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569 monitoring. While our proposed method, AnchorBERT, offers improved per-
570 formance through the modeling of emotion interrelations, we recognize that
571 emotion detection is a subjective and culturally nuanced task. The use of
572 automated emotion analysis tools must therefore be approached with care
573 and contextual awareness.

574 Our experiments are conducted on publicly available datasets, primarily
575 in English, with the inclusion of one Chinese dataset (NLPCC 2018). While
576 this provides some linguistic diversity, we acknowledge that the cultural in-
577 terpretation and expression of emotions can vary significantly across regions
578 and populations. Future work should explore broader cross-cultural evalu-
579 ation to better understand potential biases in emotion representation and
580 model behavior.

581 We also acknowledge the potential misuse of emotion detection systems,
582 such as their application in surveillance, behavioral profiling, or manipula-
583 tive content targeting. Our method was developed for academic research
584 and should not be deployed in high-stakes decision-making settings without
585 thorough fairness, accountability, and transparency assessments. We encour-
586 age future researchers and practitioners to consider these ethical implications
587 when applying models like AnchorBERT in real-world scenarios.

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593 are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of
594 the European Union - European Commission. Neither the European Com-
595 mission nor the European Union can be held responsible for them.

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Introduced emotion anchors to capture emotion interrelations in binary classifiers.

Improved multi-label text emotion detection accuracy and F1-scores.

Achieved robust performance across supervised and domain adaptation settings.

Demonstrated generalizability to various multi-label tasks and datasets.

Reduced computational complexity by leveraging pre-calculated embeddings.

Journal Pre-proof

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Ioannis Pitas reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Vasileios Mygdalis reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Polydoros Giannouris reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.
